
Culturing Sūrya Therapy in Overcoming the Covid-19 Pandemic at the Bali-Hindu Community in Mataram

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to find the cultivation of healthy living values using *sūrya* therapy strategies taught in Vedic teachings to the Hindu community in Mataram, West Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia, especially in preventing the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic. This study uses an interpretive qualitative method which is presented in the form of narrative text. The results of this study found three new findings that can be used as recommendation to related parties. *First*, the *sūrya* therapy as a countermeasure against pathogenic microorganisms is contained in the Hindu scriptures, especially in the scripture of "Catur Veda Samhita", which is believed by Hindu saints and Hindu intellectuals in Mataram to prevent the spread of the covid-19 pandemic. *Second*, *sūrya* therapy taught in Hindu religious scriptures has synergy with modern health care systems. This phenomenon is indicated by a number of research results which found that *sūrya* light contains positive energy for the maintenance of body health. *Third*, the strategy for cultivating *sūrya* therapy can be done by habituating the tradition of sunbathing in the morning, doing activities in open spaces, utilizing vacation time in locations rich in *sūrya* light, bringing out *sūrya* energy based on a belief system through the practice of Yoga Sūrya Namaskāra.

Keywords: *Cultivation of values, sūrya therapy, Vedic teachings, the covid-19 pandemic.*

INTRODUCTION

Hindu religious teachings teach health maintenance by using the light of *sūrya* contained in the holy scriptures "Catur Veda Samhita". The maintenance of health by using *sūrya* (the use of the word *sūrya* in this study is taken from the teachings of the Vedic scriptures as one of the names of many names given to represent the majesty of the sun) light is known as *sūrya* therapy. Mantras containing the teachings of *sūrya* therapy are numerous. In this regard, there are not many Hindu communities in Mataram, West Nusa Tenggara know about the mantras in the Vedic scriptures which contain the teachings of maintaining health through *sūrya* therapy. Based on the results of polls from a number of subjects who were asked for their opinions, those who know about maintaining health through the use of exposure to *sūrya* light are relatively very small in number. Those who were used as subjects were chosen randomly based on education level, age level, category of understanding of Hindu religious teachings, and social status. The instrument used in collecting the opinion polls is in the form of a questionnaire.

The results of initial data collection related to health care using *sūrya* therapy in Hindu religious teachings indicate that most Hindus in Mataram city do not know about it. This condition is indicated by the results of the opinion polls of a number of respondents who were used as research subjects. Respondents who were used as subjects in the initial data collection of the study were categorized into activities carried out in daily life. *First*, a group of Hindu saints, such as *pandita* and *pinandita*. There are two categories of *pandita* who are used as subjects in this study, namely *pedanda* and *pandita mpu*. The *pandita* who represent Hindus who have the functionalization of *ngeloka pala sraya*, which is the leader of Hindu religious rituals and at the same time is used as a support for Hindu religious activities. *Pinandita* is a Hindu holy person who also has the authority to lead Hindu religious rituals at a certain level. *Second*, the intellectual group that comes from elements of Hindu scholars. *Third*, the majority of Hindu community groups who in their daily life are more likely to carry out Hinduism in its ritual aspects.

The initial data obtained based on the results of the opinion poll represent the relatively low knowledge and understanding of Hindus in the city of Mataram regarding *sūrya* therapy in Hinduism as a vehicle for health maintenance. Based on the results of filling out a randomly selected questionnaire as many as 15% of respondents who have knowledge about *sūrya* therapy in health care come from Hindu saints and intellectuals. Respondents who do not know *sūrya* therapy in Hindu teachings with a composition of 85% who come from mostly Hindus. This condition is very reasonable because the respondents who come from Hindu saints and intellectuals have a habit of deepening the teachings of Hinduism so it is very natural for them to know about the various teachings contained in the teachings of Hinduism. On the other hand, those who are Hindu respondents mostly focus on aspects of ritual implementation and do not study much about the *tattwa* aspects of Hinduism.

Departing from the above phenomenon, it is very necessary to do research for the cultivation of *sūrya* therapy as a vehicle for health maintenance. In this regard, it is necessary to focus on three important aspects that need to be studied in this research, namely (1) how is the general description of *sūrya* therapy in the Vedic scriptures understood by Hindu

saints and Hindu intellectuals in Mataram? (2) how is the teaching of the *sūrya* therapy with modern health science in general? (3) what is the strategy in cultivating the *sūrya* therapy as an effort to maintain health in preventing the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic? The results of the analysis are used as a basis for conveying recommendations to the public regarding the benefits of *sūrya* therapy in health care, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic.

METHODS

Research design

This research is designed in an interpretive qualitative research type. This research is designed in the form of a text study which is equipped with field data. The stages of this research were initiated by conducting a text study, namely the *sūrya* therapy contained in the “Catur Veda Samhita” scriptures. The concentration of data sources is on the Ṛg Veda Samhita because in this scripture which contains the teachings of *sūrya* therapy, it is relatively high in content. There are many mantras that contain teachings on health maintenance in the g Veda Samhita, but in this study only a few mantras are taken which are assumed to be very suitable for cultivating the values of healthy living. The mantras cited in this study are quoted from a number of sources found in several libraries. The original sources of the Vedic scriptures are very difficult to find in Indonesia. In order for this research to run smoothly, the Vedic scriptures which have been translated into Indonesian were used as the main source of text data.

Important mantras related to health maintenance which are quoted from several texts or books are then analyzed to find important values for health maintenance. The results of the analysis of the mantras referred to are then related to the views of Hindu religious saints and Hindu intellectuals. *First*, Hindu religious saints in Mataram are categorized into two, namely *pandita* and *pinandita*. The *pandita* in this study is a Hindu holy person who has performed dual rituals such as *pedanda* and *pandita mpu*. The Hindu saints who are categorized as *pinandita* are those who have performed the *ekajati* ritual. Those who are categorized as *pinandita* are called stakeholders. *Second*, the Hindu intellectuals in this study were selected from academics, namely those who have extensive knowledge of Hinduism. The selection of Hindu intellectuals in this study is categorized into two, namely those who work as lecturers and teachers.

Data collection technique

This research uses qualitative data which is presented in the form of narrative text. Sources of research data are generally categorized into two. *First*, the data comes from the Ṛg Vedic teaching texts which contain *sūrya* therapy. *Second*, the views of Hindu saints and Hindu intellectuals in understanding *sūrya* therapy contained in the teachings of the Vedic scriptures. *Third*, the data obtained from yoga practitioners who apply the practice of the Yoga *Sūrya* Namaskāra. In this regard, research data was collected through document study, observation, and interviews. The document study was carried out by analyzing the sources of the Ṛg Vedic teachings about *sūrya* therapy. Text data collected as a vehicle to legitimize the truth that the Vedas teach about *sūrya* therapy. Observations were made on the Yoga *Sūrya* Namaskāra practice carried out by a number of Hindu communities at the research location. The observations carried out were non-participatory so that the researcher only observed yoga activities without taking an active role in yoga activities. Interviews were conducted with a number of informants who were determined based on a purposive technique. Interviews conducted with informants are not structured.

Data analysis technique

The data analysis technique in this study was carried out in three ways, namely data classification, data reduction, and data interpretation. Data classification is the stage of grouping data obtained based on data collection techniques while exploring data, either through text analysis or from yoga activities in the field. This study conducted data reduction simultaneously during data mining in the field. Data reduction in this study was through the process of selecting, concentrating attention and simplifying rough data taken from the author's notes during data collection. Data reduction in this study took place continuously during the study. This research uses interpretation analysis technique by interpreting the collected data. The interpretation of the data is carried out in order to understand the meaning implied in the Vedic teaching text which contains *sūrya* therapy as well as in the Yoga *Sūrya* Namaskāra practice which is carried out by a number of yoga practitioners among Hindus. Interpretation is carried out during the research process starting from data collection which aims to obtain meaning, especially those related to the teaching text of *sūrya* therapy and the practices Yoga *Sūrya* Namaskāra as a vehicle for maintaining health quality.

DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

Teachings of *Sūrya* Therapy in the Ṛg Veda Samhita Scripture

Sūrya therapy in the Vedic teachings can be demonstrated in a number of *mantras* from the Ṛg Veda Samhita, Sama Veda Samhita, Yajur Veda Samhita, and Atharva Veda Samhita. This study quotes several *mantras* from the Ṛg Veda which contain the teachings of *sūrya* therapy. The focus of taking on the Ṛg Veda Samhita scripture is based on the consideration that in the scriptures the content of *sūrya* therapy teachings is relatively high. The *mantras* quoted in this study are of the very essence, namely those related to the *sūrya* therapy. The source of the Ṛg Veda teachings which is used as the source of the quotation is the Ṛg Veda scripture which has been translated into Indonesian. This is based on the consideration that the Hindu community in Mataram city uses the Ṛg Veda Samhita scripture which has been

translated into Indonesian because it is easier to learn. In the following are excerpts of a number of Rg Veda *mantras* containing the teachings of *sūrya* therapy.

*Ut purastāt sūrya eti visvadr̥ṣṭo adr̥ṣṭahā,
adr̥ṣṭān sarvān jambhayan sarvāśca yātudhānyah.*

Rgveda I.191.8

Translation: The ubiquitous sunlight rising from the East eradicates all invisible germs. Sunlight destroys all visible and invisible disease-causing germs [1].

The above *mantra* mandates that the energy emitted by the *sūrya* in the morning has the power to annihilate invisible poisonous beings that can harm health. The *mantra* above mandates that the light emitted by the sun from the East in the morning is able to destroy small creatures that cause disease, both invisible and visible. Small creatures that can cause disease can be overcome by the energy contained in the emission of solar radiation. The negative effects of these pathogenic beings can be eliminated by the energy that the *sūrya* emits in the morning. The energy emitted by *sūrya* in accordance with the mandate of the above *mantra* has enormous benefits to overcome the negative effects of microorganisms originating from the surrounding environment so that it can help promote health. Referring to Nala [2], a disease caused by conditions in the surrounding environment is termed *adhidaiwika*.

The phenomenon mentioned above is corroborated by the narrative conveyed by Ida Pedanda Gde Made Oka Kaniten (an informant as a Hindu priest) who in general reveals the discourse that health care using *sūrya* light does exist in Vedic *mantras*. *Puja* (prayer according to Hindu practice) performed by *sulinggih* (another name for the Hindu religious priests) mentions glorifying *sūrya*. This shows that *sūrya* is a power that can be requested to provide guidance to worshipers. Attributing to this health-giving sunshine is also mentioned in the Vedic scriptures. Sunbathing as a vehicle for obtaining *sūrya* light is also a means of overcoming illness. In connection with this the energy contained in the *sūrya* light can overcome certain ailments.

Sūrya as a symbol of the Sun God in the Rg Veda Samhita teachings also has energy that can destroy all poisons and destroy microorganisms that can cause disease. This phenomenon is explicitly presented in the following *mantra* passage.

*Ud apaptad asau sūryah puru viśvāni jūrvan,
Adityah parvatebhyo viśvadr̥ṣṭo adr̥ṣṭahā.*

Rgveda I.191.9

Translation: The sun has risen at high altitudes destroying all poisons. The sun, which sees everything, destroys everything invisible, rises behind the top of the hill for the good of living things [3].

The above *mantra* explicitly mandates that *sūrya* has energy that can destroy all poisons that can degrade the health of the body. The light emitted by *sūrya* in accordance with the above *mantra* is believed to provide healing for a person who is sick due to certain poison. The energy emitted by *sūrya* has the power to destroy microorganisms that can spread disease. In the universe there are various types of invisible creatures that can spread disease to other living things, especially humans. The energy emitted by the *sūrya* through its radiation has the ability to destroy these invisible creatures so that it does not have an impact on decreasing the quality of the health of other living beings, especially humans. The utilization of *sūrya* light in the above *mantra* is very important for all beings in maintaining their existence.

In synergy with the phenomenon above, *sūrya* is able to eliminate poisons that can reduce physical and spiritual health even though it is relatively far from the earth, but the energy emitted through its light is able to substitute poison into an entity that is very beneficial to health. Here is a spell that mandates that *sūrya* energy is capable of converting poison into sweet “ambrosia” which is beneficial for health maintenance.

*Sūrye viṣam ā sajāmi dṛtiṁ surāvato gr̥he,
so cin nu na marāti no vayan̄ marāmāre asya
yojanam̄ hariṣṭhā madhu tvā madhulā cakāra.*

Rgveda I.191.10

Translation: We infuse poison in the sun, like a leather bottle in the house of an alcoholic. Truly, the sun will not die, nor will we die; because even though it is far away, but with all the might of its rays, it will destroy the poison suddenly. Antidote science will change the poison into sweet ambrosia [3].

The essence of the final part of the above *mantra* mandates that *sūrya* light has the ability to destroy poison. Antidote science will turn poison into sweet ambrosia. The above *mantra* explicitly mandates that the *sūrya* or sun has a very powerful energy to eliminate negative influences, such as poison being a useful entity for the maintenance of health. According to I Nyoman Murba Widana (an informant, a Hindu saint and a scientist), stated that *sūrya* energy has been believed as a power as a gift from God so that negative aspects for living things can be positive which is useful for living things. Hindus worship the sun as a manifestation of God's power. In this regard, Wibawa [4] reveals that the sun is a

representation of energy conversion. In synergy with this, Ida Pandita Mpu Acharya Jaya Dharma Dhaksa Natha (an informant and as a Hindu priest) stated that *sūrya* in the Hindu priest's *puja* is said as a tribute because he is a source of energy on earth. The *sūrya* symbolized by the sun is the source of life. The *sūrya* light is used to prevent certain diseases from occurring. This teaching is contained in the Vedic scriptures so that the truth can be believed by Hindus. In this regard, Wibawa [4] reveals that the sun is a representation of energy conversion.

In synergy with the above *mantra*, the energy emitted by *sūrya* which is capable of eliminating the negative influence of poison in the body of a living being, the following is explicitly mandated in the following *mantra* passage.

*Iyattikā śakuntikā sakā jaghāsa te viṣam,
so cin nu na marāti no vayaṁ marāmāre asya
yojanam hariṣṭhā madhu tvā madhulā cakāra.*
Rgveda I.191.11

Translation: This insignificant little bird has swallowed your poison; he will not die, nor will we die; because even though it is far away, with all its rays, the sun will destroy the poison suddenly and the science of antidote will turn the poison into sweet ambrosia [3].

The above *mantra* also essentially mandates that the *sūrya* light is very useful for removing the effects of poison and through the science of antidote to turn poison into sweet ambrosia. Based on the *mantra*, it can also be interpreted as the power of sunlight in eliminating small microorganisms that can produce toxins that are detrimental to health. Regarding this belief, Ida Made Santi Adnya (an informant and head of Parisada Hindu Dharma Indonesia, West Nusa Tenggara Province) stated that there are a number of microorganisms that can cause disease. The *sūrya* light is believed to be able to prevent diseases caused by very small creatures. This has been socialized to the public through the media, such as religious broadcasting on television. Referring to Monintja, et al. [5] that with sufficient sunlight can overcome TB disease. This disease is caused by mycobacterium tuberculosis.

The mandates of the *mantra* above that *sūrya* light has benefits in maintaining health. In synergy with the above *mantra*, the following is a *mantra* that mandates that *sūrya* light has the potential to get rid of several diseases.

*Udyan adya mitramaha ārohan uttarām divam,
hṛdrogam mama sūrya harimānam ca nāśaya.*
Rgveda I.50.11

The morning sun, has a potential *Mitra* (oxygen) and goes up in the sky, getting rid of my heart disease, jaundice, and anemia [1].

Based on the *mantra* above the *sūrya* has the potential to get rid of heart disease, jaundice, and anemia. The benefits of light ray from the *sūrya* (sunlight) to overcome several diseases have also been researched by modern health scientists. According to Pusparini [6] that vitamin D deficiency can cause several diseases, one of which is cardiovascular. Sunlight can prevent jaundice reported by Puspitosari, et al. [7] that exposure to the morning sun has an effect on decreasing the signs of icterus in physiological neonatorum icterus. According to Fimela [8] basking in the sun in the morning for ten minutes can prevent anemia.

In synergy with the above *mantra*, the *sūrya* is also believed to be a power that radiates all things that give glory to living beings, especially humans. This glory is indicated by adhering to high moral values and also releasing suffering, as learned in the following *mantra*.

*Udyann adya mitramaha ārohann uttarām divam,
hṛdrogam mama sūrya harimānam ca nāśaya.*
Rgveda I.50.11

Translation: Radiating with beneficial virtues, emerging and engraved into the highest moral values, O God who radiates itself, let go of the suffering of our hearts and weaknesses of our bodies [3].

According to the above *mantra*, the *sūrya* which emits light imparts benevolent energy which can lead to profitable paths, when arising can attach to the highest values of morality which can lead to an orderly life. *Sūrya* is believed to be a supernatural power that emits light capable of eliminating suffering in the hearts of devotees. It is very important to convey in the above *mantra*, that *sūrya* is believed to be able to eliminate weaknesses in the human body. In this regard, when the weaknesses that exist in the human body have disappeared, of course they will be replaced by forces that can support the vitality of human life in carrying out daily activities. The important essence implicitly contained in the above *mantra* is that the energy emitted by *sūrya* can increase body resistance (immunity) so that through this power it can defend itself from disease attacks, especially those caused by viruses and bacteria.

The above *mantra* also means that *sūrya* is believed to represent the Supernatural Power which physically emits its own light as a power believed to give life enlightenment. In this regard, *sūrya* becomes the focus of attention in worship to obtain the gift of light rays that can illuminate the path to the goal of life. The narrative mandated in the part of the *mantra* "emerging and imprinted into the highest moral values" quoted in the above *mantra* implies that *sūrya* as Supernatural Power as the source of life whose existence follows the law of the *rta* (The law of natural order according to the Hindu teachings) is a role model for all entities in the "solar system" space. Regarding the law of *rta*, Yasmini [9] stated that God created the law of *rta* to regulate the universe.

In following the laws of morality so as to create an orderly nature. Humans as elements of the "solar system" must be able to follow the laws of morality in maintaining self-order and social order in order to create a harmonious life. The pattern of living in harmony, both internally with oneself and externally with entities that exist outside of itself, has a disposition to build calm and happiness. Humans who have been able to manifest peace and happiness in themselves can create a healthy life physically and mentally. *Sūrya* is believed to be the source of life as well as a supernatural power that can provide a path to a healthy life.

Benefits of *Sūrya* Therapy Associated with Modern Health Science

Health care which is taught in Hindu teachings as stated in the previous section is a teaching that was revealed through the revelation of "Brahman" as a supernatural power which is manifested in the symbols of the gods. Health maintenance using *sūrya* therapy in Hinduism according to Ida Bagus Yoga Pramana (an informant and a yoga practitioner) is also associated with supernatural powers which are symbolized by Lord *Sūrya*, Lord Aditya, Lord Raditya, and a number of other identities which are believed to be able to give life to living beings in the world and at the same time as energy that can provide health to the world. Living things by using the light they emit. The energy contained in *sūrya* light is able to maintain health by irradiating the bodies of living beings or entities that are used for the needs of living beings.

Exposure to light emitted by *sūrya* in the perspective of modern health science has two effects, namely positive and negative. The positive impact has an influence on the quality of health, both physically and spiritually. This positive impact is given, especially by ultra violet (UV) light in certain wavelengths that can be useful for the maintenance of human health. On the other hand, the negative impact it causes is a decrease in the quality of physical and spiritual health. One of these negative impacts is given by ultra violet (UV) light with a certain wavelength. Ultraviolet (UV) rays are a category of invisible rays so that using ordinary eyesight cannot be observed.

The positive and negative impacts emitted by *sūrya* light are highly dependent on the wavelengths it radiates which are associated with the process of generating energy. The *sūrya* energy emitted has a wavelength that refers to Isfardiyana and Safitri [10] categorized into two. *First*, there is a visible light from the sun with a wavelength of more than 400 nm. Light with wavelengths above 400 nm can still be seen by the human eye directly. *Second*, light that is invisible to the eye, which is emitted with a wavelength of 10 nm to 400 nm. Light emitted with this wavelength that cannot be seen by the eye is called ultraviolet light.

The light emitted by *sūrya* in the positive dimension has energy that can eradicate a number of micro-organisms that can reduce the quality of body health. *Sūrya* therapy is carried out when the sun is still in the east or still early in the morning, because at that time the radiant energy is very helpful in overcoming the negative effects of micro-organisms that attack the body's health. The amount of light needed to cope with disease attacks depends on the type of disease that enters the body. Allergic diseases, such as itching, scabies, eczema, and tinea versicolor refer to Wibawa [4] who can use *sūrya* therapy by sunbathing at the time the sun has just risen, around 06.30 to 07.30. The duration of the irradiation time to overcome these diseases is one hour and should not be more.

Sūrya therapy which is carried out by sunbathing in the morning at 06.30 to 07.30 as described above is very effective in eliminating a number of diseases caused by microorganisms that cause allergic diseases manifested in itching, scabies, eczema. as well as tinea versicolor that appears in certain body parts. These diseases are categorized as diseases caused by bacteria and fungi. Microorganisms in the form of bacteria and fungi will not be able to reproduce if the affected body parts are exposed to sunlight regularly at the time mentioned above. The effectiveness of solar light which can optimally overcome microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi for one hour. This time duration is assumed to be sufficient to produce energy that can break the chain of development of microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi in the body. *Sūrya* energy that is absorbed by the body at the right time and duration serves to maintain a healthy body from attacks by bacteria and fungi that cause the diseases mentioned above.

Modern health care also teaches about the importance of irradiating the body with *sūrya* light to maintain health. According to Anggraini [11] that solar light can nourish the body with vitamin D and prevent the transmission of the corona virus (Covid-19). Solar light is emitted from 10:00 to 11:00 to get maximum vitamin D. Vitamin D can increase body immunity so that able to prevent transmission of the corona virus (Covid-19). The light emitted by *sūrya* in the morning before 10:00 and in the afternoon after 11:00 does not provide much benefit to the acquisition of vitamin D. The

duration of time required for irradiation is between 10 to 15 minutes because the duration of time is maximum to get vitamin D, if more than that will cause skin damage.

The above narration implies that in modern health sciences have found a link between solar light absorbed by the body and the production of vitamin D. Exposure to solar light emitted from 10:00 to 11:00 in the morning before noon when it hits the skin has energy that can convert provitamin D into Vitamin D is very useful for increasing the body's immunity. The increased immunity in the optimum composition becomes an antidote to the entry of diseases, especially those caused by the corona virus (Covid-19). The optimum intensity that can produce vitamin D requires a duration of 10 to 15 minutes because the specified duration is sufficient to meet energy needs in producing vitamin D needed by the body. The availability of sufficient vitamin D in the body affects the body's strength in maintaining health, especially in producing immunity for the body's immunity in tackling disease attacks.

Vitamin D which has an important role in strengthening the body's immune in the perspective of modern health science is also expressed by Ahsan, *et al.* [12] that vitamin D is not only used as a nutrient but also as a hormone. Vitamin D can be synthesized from the body with the help of sunlight. Sources of vitamin D can be obtained from food. The function of vitamin D is to maintain bone health and play a role in the immune system, including the immune response to viruses. People who are deficient in vitamin D will be susceptible to the risk of upper respiratory tract infections, including influenza. A study conducted on 11,321 people showed that the consumption of this vitamin at a dose of 50 mcg per day can protect the body against respiratory tract infections. The dose is equivalent to 200 grams of mackerel per day for adults.

Based on the narrative above, there is one entity that is very important in maintaining the body's immunity, namely the availability of vitamin D. The vitamin D in the body is very important in its function in maintaining the body's immunity because this vitamin will be able to cope with attacks carried out by viruses on the body. Vitamin D in the body can be synthesized with the help of solar light. The energy contained in solar light is able to synthesize vitamin D in the body as a guard for the body's immunity. Modern Health Theory in this context positions solar light as a very important entity as energy that can produce vitamin D in the body. The strength of immunity supported by the availability of vitamin D can overcome the corona virus attack into the body. This condition means that by irradiating the body with solar light at the time specified above, it can overcome the exposure of the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Exposure to *sūrya* light has the power to synthesize vitamin D which is needed by the body. The solar light that hits the body has adequate power in synthesizing vitamin D. Referring to Fiannisia [13] that vitamin D synthesized with the help of sunlight is the body's main vitamin D supply and lasts longer than vitamin D derived from food sources. Vitamin D deficiency is also caused by the presence of sunscreen, so that the body lacks vitamin D. In this regard, according to Setiati [14] UVB exposure to sunlight at the optimum time can increase the concentration of 25(OH)D significantly. This study was conducted in the tropics on a group of elderly women.

Based on the description above, there is a synergism of *sūrya* therapy between what is mandated in the teachings of Hinduism and the benefits of *sūrya* (sun) light generated from modern health research. This synergism essentially positions solar light as energy that is very important in realizing health, both physically and spiritually. The energy contained in *sūrya* light according to Hindu religious teachings can help nourish the body both preventively and curatively. The energy emitted in a preventive manner can increase the body's immunity which has implications for physical and spiritual health. Synergizing with that, in modern health science it has also been found that solar light emitted in certain waves, especially in UVB waves can produce vitamin D in the body which has the disposition to increase the body's immune balance so that it can cope with disease attacks, such as the corona virus. Utilization of the energy contained in solar light at the right time and at the right time can be used to help cope with the outbreak of disease, especially in stemming disease due to exposure to the Covid-19 pandemic that is spreading today.

It is very important to maintain health in the midst of exposure to the Covid-19 Pandemic by increasing the balance of immunity so that the corona virus cannot attack the body. A balanced body immunity can be a strong guard against virus attacks. In synergy with that, Fradanti [15] revealed that there were three sub-categories of threats and two sub-categories of vulnerability that received high index scores and eight sub-categories that received low index scores related to this corona virus. Referring to Ahsan, et al [12] that the entry of the virus into the body will be determined by the immune system in the next process. Ideally, the virus will be eliminated by the immune system. The immune conditions in the human body are not the same. This immunity causes not everyone who is exposed to the Corona virus to be sick and symptomatic. Not all of the exposure to the Corona virus in the body of an infected patient does not lead to severe lung inflammation. In another part, according to Anggraini [11], *sūrya* (sun) light can nourish the body with vitamin D and prevent transmission of the corona virus (Covid-19). *Sūrya* light is emitted at 10:00 to 11:00 to obtain maximum vitamin D. The vitamin D can increase the body's immunity so that it can prevent the transmission of the corona virus (Covid-19). According to Holick MF in Yosephin, et al.[16] that sun exposure is the best source of vitamin D and there are no cases of intoxication of vitamin D due to light exposure excess sun.

Based on the narrative above, the most important action taken is to maintain the balance of body immunity so that exposure to the Corona virus cannot cause severe lung inflammation. Increasing the balance of the body's immunity can be done by producing vitamin D with the help of *sūrya* light. In addition, according to Fiannisia [13], that vitamin D is used to prevent degenerative diseases to malignancy.

Based on the description above, the *sūrya* energy mandated in the Vedic *mantra* is in synergy with the results of modern medical research, particularly with regard to the benefits of *sūrya* light for health maintenance. In this regard, *sūrya* therapy, namely the use of sunlight as energy to increase body immunity, can avoid the negative effects of attack by microorganisms in the form of viruses and bacteria. The outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic caused by a virus can be countered by regularly shining *Sūrya* light. Utilization of *sūrya* light as mentioned in the previous section can help produce the production of vitamin D which is necessary for building health and mental health.

Cultivating Strategies for the *Sūrya* Therapy

The response to the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic in this study recommends the inculturation of *sūrya* therapy as a vehicle to increase the body's immunity so that the corona virus that causes the Covid-19 pandemic cannot reproduce normally. In the following, a number of strategies are proposed for cultivation the *sūrya* therapy in daily life, namely habituating the tradition of sunbathing in the morning, doing activities in open spaces, utilizing vacation time in locations rich in *sūrya* light, bringing out *sūrya* energy based on a belief system through the practice of Yoga *Sūrya* Namaskāra.

First, habituation of the tradition of sunbathing in the morning. Building good habits to maintain physical and spiritual health is very important, especially during the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Sūrya* light that emits rays with certain wavelengths that can help increase the body's immunity in anticipating exposure to the Covid-19 pandemic can be used to help maintain immunity at a relatively low cost. This phenomenon is indicated by the use of *sūrya* light which can be obtained freely according to needs without having to spend money to pay for it. The use of *sūrya* light has not become a tradition carried out by the wider community to maintain body health. In this regard, efforts are needed to build awareness to utilize the sun's light as optimally as possible in helping to maintain health.

The cultivation of *sūrya* therapy through absorption of sunlight in the morning in overcoming various diseases can be done from an early age. Children at an early age are trained to irradiate *sūrya* light in the morning so that it becomes a form of habituation until they are adults. Inculturation of *sūrya* therapy from an early age is actually very important to habituate them to realize the importance of irradiating by basking in the sun's rays in the morning as stated in the previous section. Inculturation of *sūrya* therapy is a natural process to maintain physical and spiritual health, because apart from being taught in the teachings of Hinduism, it is also associated with the development of modern health science which is very harmonious. Utilization of solar light energy as an effort to strengthen the body's immunity so that microorganisms that can destroy health can be overcome so that the body can maintain its health.

Habituation to illuminate the body to children from an early age is very much determined by the awareness that grows from parents in the family environment. This awareness is actualized by teaching children to *mekinyah* (sunbathing in the morning). Based on the results of observations as a reinforcement of research data, in the family life of the Balinese-Hindu society the *mekinyah* tradition has been commonly practiced since the children were infants. This tradition is done to provide absorption of solar light energy through the baby's skin. The ray of *sūrya* energy absorbed through the skin will greatly assist the body's metabolism which in its accumulation can provide benefits for maintaining health, both physically and spiritually. This belief has been taught in the teachings of the Vedic scriptures, as discussed in the previous section.

Second, making outdoor activities. The absorption of solar light by the body can be done by deliberately basking in the sun or it can also be done without leaving the activity that is being carried out. The body irradiation has intentionally been stated in the previous section which frees oneself from daily activities. The way to get *sūrya* light by continuing to carry out activities is to do activities as much as possible in an open space that can be in direct contact with sunlight. There are a number of ways that can be taken to implement this strategy, such as temporarily moving the workplace to an open space that is in direct contact with sunlight, opening the workplace ventilation as wide as possible so that when needed solar light can be carried out immediately, bringing work to be done on the spot. who can receive *sūrya* light at certain times that are useful for health maintenance, and design the workplace facing the rising sun. Rimahardika [17] states that indoor activities do not get enough sunlight.

Third, use of vacation time in *sūrya* light exposure areas. Vacation is a trend that occurs today as a return of energy after doing routine activities every day. Vacations can also build a new spirit to carry out the next routine. The time chosen to take a vacation is very varied which is adjusted to the time lag at work or can also be conditioned by needs. Holidays in general can be enjoyed by people who work in a work organization on weekends, namely Saturdays and Sundays. There is also an effective use of the day for vacation by taking time off at work. Religious holidays are also designated as national holidays in Indonesia. The Indonesian government also provides holidays in the form of "*cuti*

Bersama” (communal leave) on days that are close to religious holidays. This opportunity can be used well to build a balance of immunity in order to maintain a healthy body.

Departing from the above tendency, vacation is an activity that is very important to do in order to increase new enthusiasm in dealing with daily routines. In this regard, in choosing a vacation, of course, consider a place that fits your vacation plans. The emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic is of course also a very special consideration in choosing a vacation spot. Departing from the analysis above which positions the importance of solar light in improving the quality of health, especially in helping to increase the body's immunity so that in choosing vacation spots, of course choosing a location that is rich in solar radiation. There are two advantages that can be obtained by taking vacations in places that are rich in *sūrya* light, namely (1) someone can enjoy holidays according to your needs to increase your new spirit in carrying out daily activities; (2) being able to receive solar energy as a tool to increase the body's immunity as a preventive measure against disease attacks, especially the Covid-19 pandemic. The choice of a vacation location that considers the importance of obtaining solar light to obtain an increase in the quality of life.

Fourth, delivering faith-based *sūrya* energy through practices of Yoga *Sūrya* Namaskāra. The *Sūrya* Namaskāra Yoga is a yoga practice that is actualized by a number of people which essentially concentrates the mind on *Sūrya* as a power that can bestow health on those who practice it. The practice of Yoga *Sūrya* Namaskāra according to I Wayan Rudiarta (an informant and yoga practitioner) emphasizes the regulation of the breath known as *prāṇāyāma* as the basis for mind control. The movements performed in the practice of Yoga *Sūrya* Namaskāra are also accompanied by chanting of mantras in order to better concentrate the mind. Mantras are recited gradually according to the stages of movement performed by the body.

The mantra referring to Svami Rama [18] is a syllable, a sound, a word, or an arrangement of words acquired by is when they are in deep meditation. Mantra is not a language spoken by humans. The sounds received from the subconscious will lead the seeker of truth to higher consciousness and the higher he attains complete silence. The higher one's consciousness, the mantra will show a new meaning. Mantras like this allow one to become increasingly aware of the existence of a higher dimension of consciousness. Mantras are essentially the same as humans who have various layers of the body, namely the gross, subtle, finer, and most subtle layers of the body. In this regard, analogies such as AUM are three letters that actually represent the three bodily activities (wake up, dream, and sleep) or also represent the three bodies in the form of gross, subtle, and more subtle. But the fourth form of a mantra is the most subtle, silent and undefined.

The practice of *Sūrya* Namaskāra Yoga which is accompanied by chanting of mantras if it is associated with aspects of the belief system is also a representation of worship to the highest yoga teacher. According to Wirawan [19] that recently the Yoga *Sūrya* Namaskāra and its training system have become increasingly popular. Referring to Suamba [20] Shiva is a teacher of yoga, music, and other sciences known as *Daksina-murti*. Accordingly, Shiva sat facing south while teaching *ṛṣi* yoga and *jñāna* which are hereinafter also known as *Daksina-murti*. *Daksina-murti* is further viewed from four different aspects, namely as a yoga teacher called Yoga-daksina-murti, as a vina teacher called Vinadhara-daksina-murti, as a jnana teacher called Jñāna-daksina-murti, and as the creator of *shastra-shastra* (science of) another is called “*Vakhyana-daksina-murti*”.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, there are three conclusions. *First*, the source of Hindu teaching contains the *sūrya* therapy, namely the use of sunlight in maintaining health. The main source of *sūrya* therapy teachings is contained in the “Catur Veda Samhita” scriptures, particularly the Rg Veda which contains relatively many *mantras* which teach the importance of performing *sūrya* therapy. *Sūrya* therapy mandated in the Rg Veda teachings essentially provides guidance for health care by utilizing direct sunlight, especially in the morning. *Sūrya* therapy in this study is limited to reciting a number of *mantras* that are essential for health maintenance, both through increasing body immunity and in overcoming the attack of pathogenic microorganisms that can reduce the quality of health. *Second*, *sūrya* therapy taught in Hindu religious scriptures has synergy with modern health care systems. This phenomenon is indicated by a number of research results which found that *sūrya* light contains positive energy for the maintenance of body health. The energy emitted by *sūrya* helps maintain a healthy body, especially that which is emitted in the morning. Solar (*sūrya*) radiation that can be used to increase the body's immunity in dealing with exposure to the Covid-19 pandemic in the form of invisible light (UVB) which helps increase vitamin D production. *Third*, the inculturation strategy of solar therapy can be done by habituation of the tradition of sunbathing in the morning, doing activities in open spaces, the use of vacation time in a location rich in *sūrya* light, bringing forth *sūrya* energy based on a belief system through the practice of the *Sūrya* Namaskāra Yoga.

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